

Synthesis and Biological Activities of some 7-Aryl-3-arylideneimino-5-thiono-1,4,6,7-tetrahydropyrimido[4,5-d]-imidazol-2-ones

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7-Aryl-3-arylideneimino 5-thiono-1,4,6,7-tetrahydropyrimido[4,5 d]imidazol-2-ones (4) have been synthesised by the condensation of 5-arylidene-3-arylideneimino-hydantoins (3) and thioureas in methanolic sodium hydroxide. The compounds have been screened for their fungicidal activity

A perusal of literature reveals that among many pesticidal nitrogen and sulphur heterocyclics, a strong feature for their activities is the presence

Scheme 1

Compound 4 may be viewed to incorporate both the above features with possible pesticidal activity. The observation coupled with the fact that fusion of two biolabile rings, viz. imidazole¹ and pyrimidine² together would give molecule 4 which may have enhanced pesticidal activities. With this objective we report the synthesis of title compounds and evaluation of their fungicidal activity.

Experimental

Condensation of arylaldehyde semicarbazones with chloroacetic acid and CH_2COONa , yielded the corresponding hydantoins which were converted into the corresponding arylidene (3) by the Knoevenagel reaction with aromatic aldehydes. The presence of $\text{C}=\text{O}$ group in α,β -unsaturated system render them available for the addition of thiourea to give the titled compounds 4 (Scheme 1).

5-Benzylidene-3-benzylideneiminohydantoin (3a): A mixture of 3-benzylideneiminohydantoin (0.01 mol, 4 g), anhydrous sodium acetate (0.01 mol, 2 g) and benzaldehyde (0.01 mol, 2 ml) in glacial acetic acid (15 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The reaction mixture was then poured into water and the resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol (3.5 g), m.p. 187° (Found: C, 69.98; H, 4.32; N, 14.29. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2$ calcd. for: C, 70.10; H, 4.46; N, 14.43%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3100 (NH), 1680 (C=O), 1620 (C=N), 1560 and 1480 cm^{-1} (Ar ring); δ (DMSO- d_6) 6.2 (1H, s, CH=N), 5.8 (1H, s, olefinic) and 6.6-7.2 (10 H, m, ArH).

Similarly, other compounds were prepared (Table 1).

7-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-3-benzylideneimino-5-thiono-1,4,6,7-tetrahydropyrimido-[4,5-d]imidazol-2-one (4b): A mixture of 5-(4-methoxy)benzylidene-3-benzylideneiminohydantoin (0.01 mol, 2.9 g), thiourea (0.11 mol, 1 g) and sodium hydroxide (0.02 mol, 0.8 g) in methanol (20 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and poured into water. The resulting solid was dried and crystallised from ethanol, (2.5 g), m.p. 163° (Found: C 60.18; H, 4.09; N, 18.37. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{S}$ calcd. for: C, 60.31; H, 4.23; N, 18.51%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3300 (NH), 1650 (C=O), 1600 (C=N), 1580, 1480 and 1450 cm^{-1} (Ar ring); δ (DMSO- d_6) 3.4 (3H, s, OCH_3), 6.25 (1H, s, CH=N), 3.1 (1H, d, HCNH), 6.8-7.5 (9H, m, Ar), signals for NH and =NH not observed.

TABLE 1 - PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3*

Compd. no.	R	R	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %	$\nu_{\max}$ (cm ⁻¹)			δ (ppm)			
						NH	C=O	C-N	C-CH	CH=N	OCH ₃	ArH
3b	H	4-OCH ₃	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₃	185	60	3 180	1 675	1 615	5.7	6.2	4.1	6.7-7.4
3c	H	2-OH, 4-OCH ₃	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₄	220d	57	3 200	1 670	1 620	5.8	6.1	4.2	6.5-7.5
3d	H	3-NO ₂	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₄	203	60	3 200	1 680	1 620	5.8	6.2	-	6.6-7.5
3e	4-OCH ₃	H	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₃	162	63	3 190	1 672	1 612	5.7	6.2	4.1	6.7-7.3
3f	4-OCH ₃	4-OCH ₃	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄	178	61	3 195	1 680	1 620	5.7	6.1	4.2	6.5-7.6
3g	4-OCH ₃	2-OH, 4-OCH ₃	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₅	173	65	3 185	1 675	1 615	5.8	6.1	4.2	6.4-7.3
3h	3-NO ₂	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₄	224	63	3 200	1 680	1 620	5.7	6.2	-	6.6-7.6
3i	3-NO ₂	4-OCH ₃	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₃	220	62	3 195	1 675	1 615	5.8	6.2	4.1	6.5-7.3
3j	3-NO ₂	3 NO ₂	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₆ O ₃	221	63	3 185	1 670	1 620	5.8	6.1	-	6.7-7.4

*All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

TABLE 2 - PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4*

Compd. no.	R	R'	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %	$\nu_{\max}$ (cm ⁻¹)			δ (ppm)			
						NH	C=O	C-N	HC-N	HC-NH	OCH ₃	ArH
4a	H	H	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ OS	180	64	3 280	1 655	1 605	6.1	3.2	-	6.7-7.5
4c	H	2-OH, 4-OCH ₃	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S	165d	63	3 240	1 650	1 600	6.2	3.1	3.3	6.6-7.5
4d	H	3-NO ₂	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ S	159d	65	3 260	1 650	1 605	6.2	3.2	-	6.5-7.6
4e	4-OCH ₃	H	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S	156	64	3 280	1 655	1 600	6.1	3.2	3.4	6.7-7.5
4f	4-OCH ₃	4-OCH ₃	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S	169	65	3 260	1 655	1 600	6.1	3.1	3.4	6.6-7.5
4g	4-OCH ₃	2-OH, 4-OCH ₃	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S	168	68	3 280	1 650	1 605	6.2	3.2	3.3	6.5-7.6
4h	3-NO ₂	H	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ S	>220	61	3 280	1 655	1 605	6.1	3.1	-	6.6-7.6
4i	3-NO ₂	4-OCH ₃	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ S	165	63	3 240	1 650	1 600	6.2	3.1	3.4	6.7-7.4
4j	3-NO ₂	3 NO ₂	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ S	164	65	3 260	1 650	1 605	6.2	3.2	-	6.5-7.3

*All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

Similarly, other compounds were prepared (Table 2).

Antifungal activity: The antifungal activity of the titled compounds was evaluated on *Aspergillus niger* and *Helminthosporium oryzae* at concentrations of 1000, 100 and 10 ppm by the agar growth technique. The number of replications in each case being three. The results were compared with commercial fungicide carbendazim and Dithane M-45 and the percentage inhibition was evaluated.

All the compounds showed moderate inhibition (60.2-85.5%) at 1000 ppm level on both the test species. However, their inhibition power decreased very rapidly (35.7-46.0%) at 10 ppm; 4i and 4j showed 60.8 and 62.7% at 10 ppm but still their activity is not very much comparable to the commercial fungicides, carbendazim (83.5%) and Dithane M-45 (83.0%) tested under similar condition.

The activity of all the compounds was found to be more on *A. niger* than *H. oryzae*. Compounds

4i and 4j have fairly good activity than the others, indicates that combination of polar substituents like OCH₃, NO₂ or two NO₂ impart fungitoxicity.

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References

1. Kippon Chem. Ind., Jap. Pat. 157 570/1980 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1981, 95, 71995); L. ORLIKOWSKI and C. C. SHRAZYP, *Agroditw.*, 1981, 18, 47; U. P. DEV and P. K. SATYARAJAN, *Agric. Res. J. Kerala*, 1980, 18, 413 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1981, 94, 169281).
2. M. PROIVA, U. VALENTA and A. CAPEK, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1981, 94, 192373; E. F. ROTHGERY and H. A. SCHROEDER US Pat. 4 263 297/1981 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1981, 95, 62247); J. A. G. MICHAEL, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1970, 73, 130082.